

MORPHOLOGY OF THE INTERNAL RELIEF OF THE AMPULLA OF THE PHATERNAL PAPILLA AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE FOR THE CLINIC

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Abstract. *Purpose of the study. To study the morphology of internal relief and microarchitectonics of folds and flaps of the mucous membrane of the ampulla of the phaternal papilla along its length. By the method of preparation of serial histotopographic slices the internal relief of the ampulla of the phaternal papilla in adults was studied (from the archive of micropreparations of the Department of Histology). Wiring of the material and pouring into paraffin was carried out according to the generally accepted method. Sections were stained by hematoxylin-eosin, Van Gieson and Mallory methods. Consecutively studying serial slices and by mounting reconstruction of their printouts, we studied the internal relief of the ampulla of the phaternal papilla from the place of formation to its mouth.*

Keywords: *Faterov papilla, ampulla of faterov papilla, hepatic-pancreatic ampulla, internal relief, microarchitectonics of folds.*

МОРФОЛОГИЯ ВНУТРЕННЕГО РЕЛЬЕФА АМПУЛЫ ОТЕЧНОГО СОСОЧКА И ЕЕ ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ДЛЯ КЛИНИКИ

Аннотация. *Цель исследования. Изучить морфологию внутреннего рельефа и микроархитектонику складок и лоскутов слизистой оболочки ампулы отцовского сосочка по ее длине. Методом приготовления серийных гистотопографических срезов изучен внутренний рельеф ампулы отцовского сосочка у взрослых (из архива микропрепаратов отдела гистологии). Монтаж материала и заливку в парафин осуществляли по общепринятой методике. Срезы окрашивали гематоксилин-эозином, методами Ван-Гизона и Мэллори. Последовательно изучая серийные срезы и монтируя реконструкцию их отпечатков, мы изучали внутренний рельеф ампулы отцовского сосочка от места образования до ее устья.*

Ключевые слова: *Фатеров сосочек, ампула Фатерова сосочка, печеночно-поджелудочная ампула, внутренний рельеф, микроархитектоника складок.*

Results. It has been established that the mucous membrane of the ampulla of the phaternal papilla forms many anastomosing folds, which form a trabecular network. The folds are

multistoreyed, the free ends of distal folds are arranged in a tile-like manner, overlapping each other. It is assumed that when the pressure in the duodenal cavity increases, they close tightly, preventing the retrograde flow of the intestinal contents into the ampulla cavity.

Introduction. The study of the structure of the great duodenal papilla is devoted to the works of a number of researchers [1,5,7]. Intensive development of endoscopic technique has led to wide use of its achievements in diagnostics and treatment of diseases of internal organs, in general, and diseases of biliary system in particular. It occurs against the background of some lag of morphological substantiation of these manipulations and explanation of mechanisms of pathogenesis of their complications. One of the diagnostic investigations of the ampulla of the phaternal papilla is endoscopic retrograde cholangiography.

An endoscopic probe is introduced into the ampulla through its mouth in retrograde direction. According to literature sources devoted to this issue, this diagnostic manipulation often leads (about 3%) to such complications as cholangitis. pancreatitis (2). Nevertheless, in the morphological literature there are almost no comprehensive data on the causes and mechanism of development of these complications. There is also insufficient data on the microrelief of the inner surface and on the microarchitectonics of the mucous membrane formations of the ampulla of the phaternal papilla throughout its entire length, from the site of formation to the mouth.

Purpose of the study. To study the internal relief and microarchitectonics of the mucous membrane formations of the ampulla of the phaternal papilla throughout its entire length.

Material and Methods. We have studied the internal relief of the ampulla of the phaternal papilla of adult humans (using archival materials of the Department of Histology) by the method of preparation of serial histotopographic sections. A total of 8 organocomplexes fixed in 12% neutral formalin were studied. A flap of the duodenum wall from the place of the common bile and pancreatic ducts entry into its wall to the lower border of the ampulla mouth was cut out.

Wiring of the material and pouring into paraffin was carried out according to the generally accepted technique.

The whole material was "planted" in one block and serial histotopographic sections were obtained. The whole material was cut and through every tenth four slices in a row were mounted on 4 slides. Depending on the volume of the material under study, 600 to 800 or more slices were obtained from each block. Slices were stained with hematoxylin-eosin, Van Gieson and Mallory methods. The internal relief of the ampulla of the phaternal papilla from the place of formation to its orifice was studied by sequentially studying serial sections and by mounting reconstruction of their printouts.

Results and their discussion. The ampulla of the phaternal papilla in humans in most cases is formed as a result of fusion of the common bile and pancreatic ducts inside the duodenal wall.

The shape of the cavity depends on the level of fusion of these ducts. In high fusion of the ducts the shape of the cavity is cylindrical, and in low fusion it is oval and round. In almost all cases above the large papilla of the duodenum, in the thickness of which the ampulla of the phaternal papilla is located, the duodenal mucosa forms a fold accompanying the ampulla. As the diameter of the ampulla increases, the fold decreases in size and smooths out somewhat.

Apparently, it creates a reserve of tissue elements for the expansion of the ampulla when it is filled with digestive juices. The ampulla of the phaternal papilla has mucous, submucous, muscular and adventitial membranes. From the outside of the duodenal cavity it is covered by its mucous membrane. Protruding into the duodenal cavity, the part of the phaternal papilla is covered on all sides by the intestinal mucosa. The mucous membrane of the ampulla is lined with single-layer prismatic epithelium. In the proximal part of the ampulla its mucous membrane forms longitudinal folds. They are elevated distally and anastomoses appear between them.

Transverse sections of the ampulla reveal a trabecular network consisting of anastomosing folds. The folds are covered on both sides by prismatic epithelium and are based on loose, unformed connective tissue. Distally, the height of the folds increases and the configuration of the anastomoses becomes more complex.

In the vicinity of the orifice, the construction of these folds close together, and they somewhat resemble the arrangement of rose petals at the tip of the bud. This design of the folds suggests that the higher the pressure inside the duodenal cavity, the tighter the free ends of these folds close together, reliably preventing regurgitation of the intestinal contents into the ampulla.

Some authors (6) assume the presence of flaps in the ampulla cavity, also preventing regurgitation of the intestinal contents into it. In the most distal part, i.e. at the mouth of the ampulla, the folds become longitudinal and parallel to the ampulla outlet channel. At the mouth of the ampulla, the free ends of the folds are arranged in a multi-storied manner, overlapping each other. Apparently, when the pressure in the duodenum increases, they close tightly, blocking the way of regurgitation of the intestinal contents into the ampulla. We have studied the ratio of the area of folds and flaps of the ampulla mucosa, on the area of its free space, on serial consecutive transverse sections of the ampulla. It was found that the average area occupied by the flaps on transverse sections averaged 27.6 ± 0.69 and the free space area $4.5 \pm 0, 29$. The area of folds is about 6 times greater than the area of free space.

Discussion of the findings. The results of our studies indicate that inside the ampulla of the phaternal papilla there is a complex consisting of folds and flaps. At the mouth of the ampulla, these folds have free mobile ends. These folds are multi-storied and have complex anastomoses between them. There is an increase in the number and density of these folds in the proximal-distal direction. Our comparative morphological studies from previous years (4,5) have confirmed the presence of such folds and flaps in laboratory animals as well. It can be assumed that retrograde introduction of the probe into the ampulla cavity of the phaternal papilla, in the presence of the preserved complex of folds and flaps, can disturb their normal architectonics.

It can create an obstacle to normal outlet of bile and pancreatic juice into the duodenal cavity and to regurgitation of duodenal contents into the ampulla. Some of the complications of this manipulation seem to be connected with this. Nature, represented by a complex of folds and flaps, has created a reliable barrier preventing retrograde flow of duodenal contents into the ampulla cavity. This must be taken into account when carrying out instrumental diagnostic manipulations in it.

Conclusion. The ampulla of the pharyngeal papilla contains a complex of numerous, complexly arranged and anastomosing folds. They are arranged in several stages, and the free ends of the distal folds close at the mouth like the ends of the petals of a rosebud. When the pressure in the duodenal cavity increases, these folds close tightly, reliably blocking the path of retrograde flow of intestinal contents into the ampulla cavity. It can be assumed that retrograde cannulation of the ampulla of the phaternal papilla with preserved valve and fold apparatus of the ampulla of the phaternal papilla can damage the normal architectonics of this complex. This should be taken into account when planning therapeutic and diagnostic manipulations in it.

Certainly, we are far from the opinion that the results of our morphological study obtained during the study of the ampulla of the phaternal papilla in healthy people and laboratory animals should be directly transferred to the clinic, but there is something to think about in this complex process.

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